

Enhanced Routing for Serverless Functions: A Performance-based Approach with Runtime Adaptation

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Abstract—Serverless computing has reshaped the cloud computing landscape by offering benefits such as auto-scalability, streamlined operational management, and granular billing. As its adoption grows, challenges related to performance optimization in hybrid architectures combining private servers and public cloud clusters have emerged. Central to these challenges are achieving optimal response latency and balancing performance and cost. To address these challenges, this paper introduces an adaptive routing service specifically designed for hybrid environments, proficient in leveraging real-time function metrics. Our proposed service pivots on three integral components: a monitor that captures performance metrics and raises alarms for predefined anomalies; a forecaster that predicts function latency across clusters, which includes wait and execution times, and produces request distributions for each cluster to equalize the overall function latency; and a router then processes incoming requests, taking cues from the forecaster’s predictions. Notably, based on user-defined objectives, the forecaster can be directed to either minimize latency or optimize execution costs. Comprehensive evaluations on AWS and Azure using Apache OpenWhisk clusters showcase our approach’s effectiveness, yielding a 9% improvement in average latency, a 45% decrease in standard deviation latency and a 17% cost reduction compared to conventional 50-50 routing. The advantages of elevated monitoring frequency are also illuminated, emphasizing quicker convergence times.

Index Terms—serverless computing, function-as-a-service, runtime adaptation, openwhisk, performance forecasting, routing

I. INTRODUCTION

Serverless computing, commonly referred to as Function as a Service (FaaS), has garnered significant attention in recent years due to its numerous advantages, including auto-scalability, diminished operational management, and micro-billing. In this paradigm, developers can concentrate exclu-

sively on application logic while cloud providers dynamically allocate resources, triggering functions in response to external events and scaling these functions based on demand.

However, as serverless computing continues its ascent in popularity [1], it brings forth new challenges, notably around performance optimization [2]. One critical performance metric, response latency, bears repercussions not just for the end-user experience but also impacts broader cloud resource utilization and cost paradigms [3]. In environments where functions might be deployed across a mix of private proprietary servers and public cloud clusters, like AWS or Azure, achieving optimal latency becomes a convoluted task.

Industries spanning manufacturing, eHealth, and smart agriculture often pivot to proprietary servers, driven by a blend of operational robustness, heightened security, and cost optimization considerations [4]. These dedicated servers, while bolstering data security and potentially reducing costs, are frequently complemented with public cloud alternatives. This ensures resilience, maintaining uptime during peak demands or unforeseen contingencies, especially in mission-critical operations [5]. Yet, this hybrid model, which can facilitate cost-effective operations for stakeholders, is not without its challenges. Balancing requests between private and public cloud platforms requires a finesse that traditional, policy-centric routing methods often fail to deliver [6]. These approaches fail to adapt to the dynamic nature of serverless functions, which can vary due to factors like cold starts, resource contention, or vendor-specific nuances [7].

A noteworthy feature of serverless computing is its reliance on containers for function execution, enhancing aspects like function isolation and scalable management [8]. Depending

on specific requirements, functions can be registered across diverse platforms—from public or private clouds to edge devices or even hybrid setups [9]. The FaaS platform’s role extends to managing these containers in tune with incoming request patterns, dynamically adjusting based on demand [10]. Yet, despite the advantages, concurrent container execution might impede service performance [11].

Performance, particularly in FaaS, is multifaceted and can be dissected into:

- 1) Initialization or cold start latency for preparing the function container in case of no available idle containers.
- 2) Wait latency spent inside the FaaS platform after initialization and before execution. Wait time increases when the number of function invocations exceeds the capacity of the infrastructure.
- 3) Execution latency for running the function. It defines the cost of the service and given a preset container memory and the resource capacity, execution time should be stable.

Factors like infrastructure variability, function attributes, and invocation rates can cause these latencies to fluctuate, potentially deteriorating the Quality of Service (QoS) [3].

Building on the aforementioned challenges, this work seeks to pivot the serverless computing landscape by introducing an enhanced, dynamic routing service tailored for hybrid environments. Our primary contributions can be encapsulated as follows:

- 1) **Adaptive Performance and Cost-based Routing:** We present a system that harnesses real-time function metrics- encompassing the number of invocations, memory utilization, along with wait and execution latencies - to intelligently direct serverless function requests across a spectrum of computing clusters, focusing on either amplifying performance or cost-efficiency. This dual-focused approach ensures that users are not only privy to optimal function response times but also benefit from cost-effective compute resource utilization. Unlike traditional routing methodologies, which are statically pre-configured, our approach is inherently dynamic and evolves based on prevailing performance and cost metrics.
- 2) **Integrated Monitoring, Forecasting, and Routing:** Our service amalgamates three key components:
 - A *monitor* that vigilantly observes performance metrics across clusters, thereby providing a holistic view of the system health and raising alarms upon detecting deviations from predefined performance benchmarks.
 - A predictive *forecaster* that anticipates function latency based on the most recent metrics, fine-tunes the proportion of requests designated to each cluster, and integrates cost considerations for optimal request routing. This proactive adjustment approach ensures cost and performance efficiency.

- The *router*, acting on the insights furnished by the forecaster, distributes incoming requests optimally, ensuring performance agility or cost savings.

- 3) **Holistic Evaluation:** To validate the efficacy of our proposed solution, we’ve meticulously evaluated it in real-world scenarios, incorporating two distinct Apache OpenWhisk clusters deployed on industry-leading cloud platforms: AWS and Azure. Our trials under concurrent request scenarios for single and dual functions offer proof of our service’s superiority in both performance and cost-efficiency.

Through this work, we aim to bridge the gap in the domain of hybrid serverless computing offering to stakeholders a resilient, and performance/cost-optimized solution.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II provides a review of the related works, while Section III details the architecture behind the proposed adaptive routing service, discussing its core components and their interactions. Sections IV and V present the evaluation methodology and the experimental results of our service, respectively. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper, summarizing the contributions and hinting at future research directions in this domain.

II. RELATED WORK

Understanding and predicting performance in serverless computing, especially FaaS, has been a topic of keen interest, given the dynamic nature of FaaS deployments and their nuanced performance metrics.

A. Performance Estimation in FaaS

Recently, several works have proposed analytical methods to estimate the performance of FaaS platforms leveraging evaluation metrics. SAAF [12] provides metrics of performance profiling and resource utilization of concurrent FaaS workloads to generate accurate FaaS function runtime predictions. Authors in [13] present a data-driven model that predicts the average response time of a function served by the KNative FaaS platform, with the experimental results being limited to a single server. Considering the performance overhead of concurrency, [14] proposes autoscaling mechanisms for serverless applications exploiting reinforcement learning techniques. This approach is evaluated in real and simulated environments using the Kubeless serverless platform.

Emphasizing the orchestration of functions, MLFaaS [15] proposes a novel approach to deploy a machine learning pipeline as a workflow of linked functions, with the optimal number of functions in the workflow derived from each function’s response time. Meanwhile, [16] sketches out a framework for modeling the end-to-end response latency of function workflows, leveraging metrics from AWS Lambda and using graph analysis to predict and optimize both performance and cost. SLAM [17] estimates the execution time of the functions within a serverless application to determine the optimal memory configuration for the application based on specified service level objectives and user-specified objectives.

B. Implications of Bursting Invocations and Time Series Forecasting

Highlighting the nuances of function invocation, [3] underscores the implications of bursting function invocations on a worker node, particularly its impact on wait time. [18] presents production measurements of FaaS benchmarks deployed on IBM Cloud and a private cloud to investigate the impact of workload consolidation, wait, initialization, and execution latency. The measurements indicate that the duration of a function, besides the selected memory, is also correlated to the number of concurrent containers. Drawing inspiration from these observations, works such as [19] have proposed time series forecasting approaches. In this direction, FaaST [20] harnesses temporal patterns of the invocation frequency to curtail cold-starts, especially for applications that aren't frequently invoked on Azure Functions.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

The primary goal of the proposed adaptive routing service is to dynamically route serverless function requests in hybrid environments, optimizing for the chosen user objectives such as function latency or cost. This section provides an in-depth discussion on the design and architecture of the service, detailing the interactions among its core components.

A. Overall Architecture

The system is architected around three main components illustrated in Fig.1:

- 1) **Monitor:** Observes performance metrics of the registered clusters including average init, wait and execution time. It also generates alarms when these metrics violate predefined thresholds.
- 2) **Forecaster:** Uses recent metrics to predict the expected function latency across each cluster. Depending on the user-defined objectives, it computes the percentage of requests to be routed to each cluster, optimizing for either latency (i.e., sum of wait and execution time) or cost (i.e., execution time).
- 3) **Router:** Actively distributes incoming serverless function requests according to the distribution percentages generated by the Forecaster.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Architecture of the Adaptive Routing Service.

The Monitor, Forecaster, and Router operate in tandem, continuously adapting to the environment's dynamic nature.

B. Monitor

The FaaS monitor probes the clusters and fetches essential performance metrics. Metrics include number of cold starts, success percentage of the calls and the average of wait, initialization and execution times in a time window interval. Thus the user can configure the monitor to check the previous 10 minutes of executions (the obtained averages will refer to this time interval) and they can also set a polling period (i.e. how often the monitor will poll for results refreshing the time window). Results may refer to one target function results, or if not set, to all the functions executed within the monitoring window. The supporting logic can be configured to trigger alarms (or the invocation of the Forecaster) whenever one of the obtained metrics exceeds a threshold.

C. Forecaster

The Forecaster is structured as a REST API developed using Flask with Gunicorn serving as the WSGI server [21]. This API consists of a single GET endpoint, which when triggered, initiates the process of data retrieval from the OpenWhisk metrics API¹ of each registered cluster. Data retrieval is performed in parallel through multi-threading, covering the recent 15-minute period, considering that FaaS platforms typically retain containers alive for 10 to 15 minutes. Forecaster's internal architecture and components are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Forecaster's internal Architecture and Components.

The initial step in the processing phase is data preprocessing, where the data are streamlined to a usable format. This involves retaining only relevant fields such as *activationId*, *name*, *start*, *end*, *waitTime*, *duration*, and *memory*. Subsequently, the data are aggregated with a frequency of one minute, followed by inferring the required details, including the number of activations per minute.

Post preprocessing, each function's data are fed into an exponential smoothing model [22], employing separate model instances for *duration* and *waitTime* metrics, with a smoothing level set to 0.5. This model predicts the execution and wait time for each function executed in every cluster within the last 15 minutes.

To estimate performance, the predicted duration and wait time values are summed, resulting in a performance score measured in milliseconds for each cluster. When estimating cost, the prediction involves considering the mean number of invocations and the memory used by each function, with the score being expressed in dollars.

¹<https://github.com/apache/openwhisk/blob/master/docs/metrics.md>

Following this, the absolute scores are converted to relative scores using Eq. 1.

$$\text{relative_scores}[c][m] = \left(\frac{\text{inverted_metric}[c][m]}{\sum_{c' \in C} \text{inverted_metric}[c'][m]} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

In the equation above, $\text{relative_scores}[c][m]$ calculates the relative score for a given cluster (c) and metric (m). This is achieved by dividing the inverted metric of the current cluster by the sum of the inverted metrics across all clusters, denoted as c' in the set of all clusters C . The result is then multiplied by 100 to obtain a percentage value, facilitating a direct comparison of relative scores between different clusters.

To obtain the $\text{inverted_metric}[c][m]$, we employ a reciprocal transformation of the original metric values, defined as:

$$\text{inverted_metric}[c][m] = \frac{1}{\text{metrics}[c][m]}$$

This transformation is pivotal in normalizing the metric values, subsequently allowing for a coherent formulation of the relative scores. It effectively inverts the scale of the metrics, wherein a higher original metric value will result in a lower inverted metric value, and vice versa. The summation in the denominator acts as a normalization factor, ensuring the relative scores across all clusters sum to 100, thus presenting a percentage distribution of scores across the clusters under each metric.

The derived scores are then utilized to obtain an aggregate view of the performance and cost metrics on a per-cluster basis, facilitating an informed routing decision.

Finally, these relative scores are collated into a JSON object, which is then transmitted to the Router to aid in making dynamic routing decisions. This comprehensive process ensures that the routing decisions are not just data-informed but are continually adapting to the real-time performance and cost dynamics of the system.

D. Router

The Router acts on the insights from the Forecaster, dynamically adjusting the routing of incoming requests. The Router includes a REST endpoint through which new percentages for routing can be applied dynamically at any time. In case of the primary server being completely unavailable, e.g. returning a 50X response code, all requests are forwarded to the secondary cluster by default.

IV. EVALUATION SETUP

This section details the evaluation setup which encompasses the configurations of the server and clusters, the chosen functions for the experiment, and the delineated experimental setups intended to evaluate the proposed system.

A. Server and Cluster Configuration

The adaptive routing service is constituted of the Router and the Monitor, implemented as pattern subflows running on a NodeRED server, and the Forecaster hosted within a docker container. Communication between the Router and the Monitor with the Forecaster is facilitated through HTTP nodes. The system operates on a server situated in Athens, Greece, provisioned with a single worker boasting 4 vCPUs and 8GB of RAM.

The requests (i.e., function invocations) are served by two OpenWhisk clusters, configured distinctly and hosted on AWS and AZURE platforms respectively. A comparative configuration of these clusters is presented in Table I.

TABLE I
CLUSTER CONFIGURATION COMPARISON

	AWS	AZURE
Workers	4	3
Worker Size	4 vCPU, 16GB RAM	8 vCPU, 32GB RAM
Container Memory	8GB	2GB
Location	Sweden	Netherlands
Orchestrator	Kubernetes	Kubernetes

B. Function Implementation

The evaluation process utilized two Python-native functions with differing computational demands: a function to calculate Fibonacci numbers and another to generate a large list. The Fibonacci function is tasked with determining the n -th number in the sequence, while the List function generates a list with length equal to the given n . The functions operate with default input parameters: $n=40$ for the Fibonacci function and a list length of 10 million.

C. Experimental Setups

Our experimental setup is devised to scrutinize both the performance and cost-efficiency of the adaptive routing service. We detail the setups as follows:

Performance-based Routing

- 1) Deployment of the Fibonacci function with an initial routing strategy favoring AWS (100-0) coupled with a 10-minute monitoring pooling.
- 2) Altering the monitoring pooling to 5 minutes in a setup akin to the first experiment.
- 3) A baseline experiment deploying the Fibonacci function with a static 50-50 routing strategy.
- 4) A setup involving both the Fibonacci and List functions, initiated with a 100-0 routing strategy and a 10-minute monitoring pooling.
- 5) Establishing a baseline with both functions and a fixed 50-50 routing strategy.

Cost-based Routing

- 1) An evaluation of the cost implications utilizing both functions, a 100-0 initial routing strategy, and a 10-minute monitoring pooling; with results juxtaposed against the fifth setup in the performance-based routing.

Alarms from the monitor to the forecaster towards re-estimating the routing strategy are triggered when the overall waitTime in a cluster exceeds 3 seconds.

D. Request Rate

Throughout all experimental scenarios, we maintained a consistent request rate of 10 invocations per minute for every function, to facilitate a controlled evaluation of the system’s capabilities.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Average Latencies Analysis

The experimental results, illustrated in Fig 3, elucidate the performance metrics accrued from different routing strategies implemented during the testing phase involving Fibonacci and combined (Fibonacci and List) functions.

Fig. 3. Mean Response Latency between different experiments.

Focusing initially on the Fibonacci function deployment, we observe the performance-based adaptive strategy, commencing with a 100-0 routing, encountering elevated latencies initially, with average response latency and execution time noted at 75396 ms and 57973 ms, respectively. Nevertheless, a substantial reduction is observable upon convergence for both latency and execution time. Introducing a reduced monitoring pooling interval of 5 minutes yielded comparable latencies. However, as can be seen comparing Fig. 4 and 5, this setup facilitated a 30% faster convergence compared to the 10-minute pooling interval. Meanwhile, the static strategy, operating on a 50-50 routing configuration, showcased lower initial latencies, albeit without the benefits of adaptive optimization (Fig. 6).

Extending the deployment to include both the Fibonacci and List functions, the performance-based adaptive strategy persisted in demonstrating higher introductory latencies (36825 ms response latency and 27910 ms execution time). Yet, it exhibited notable performance improvements upon reaching convergence with 36162 ms and 27179 ms in respective categories (i.e., 9% lower latency compared to the static routing (see Fig. 7 and 8)). The cost-based adaptive approach displayed initial and converged latencies of 66022 ms and 63376 ms, along with execution times starting at 28780 ms and reducing to 26249 ms post-convergence (lowest among all setups), highlights the interplay between performance and

Fig. 4. Time Series of wait and response latency with Fibonacci function, performance-based adaptation and 10 minutes monitoring pooling.

Fig. 5. Time Series of wait and response latency with Fibonacci function, performance-based adaptation and 5 minutes monitoring pooling.

cost-efficiency, where execution time is taken into account instead of the overall latency (see Fig. 9).

B. Variance Analysis

The standard deviation (STD) provides insights into the variability of the performance metrics, which in the context of latency, can be critical for applications demanding consistency. The results, depicted in Fig 10, furnish insights into the standard deviation of the response latency across different setups.

For the Fibonacci function deployment:

- The adaptive strategy exhibited high variability initially with an STD of 43494 ms for response latency. However, this drastically reduced upon convergence to 8989 ms.
- The adaptive approach with a 5-minute monitoring interval mirrored a similar trend, which upon convergence tapered to 11046 ms.
- The static strategy, in this scenario, noted around 30% higher variability in latency compared to the converged version of the first setup.

For the combined Fibonacci and List functions deployment:

- The adaptive strategy had an STD of 9176 ms (response latency) which upon convergence, this value reduced slightly to 8388 ms.
- The cost-optimized adaptive strategy showcased a high STD since it optimizes the execution time instead of the

Fig. 6. Time Series of wait and response latency with Fibonacci function and 50-50 routing policy.

Fig. 8. Time Series of wait and response latency with Fibonacci & List functions and 50-50 policy.

Fig. 7. Time Series of wait and response latency with Fibonacci & List functions, performance-based adaptation and 10 minutes monitoring pooling.

Fig. 9. Time Series of execution latency with Fibonacci & List functions, cost-based adaptation and 10 minutes monitoring pooling.

overall latency. However, it exhibited the lowest STD in execution time (7868 ms upon convergence).

- The static strategy, in this scenario, noted around 45% higher variability in latency compared to the converged version of the performance-optimized adaptive setup.

C. Cost Analysis

Table II illustrates the cost analysis for each experimental setup, denoting both the initial and converged costs. The costs are presented in terms of the mean cost per minute, which are calculated based on the average execution time and the number of requests processed each minute in each cluster for functions' memory of 512Mb.

TABLE II
COST PER EXPERIMENT

Experimental Setup	Cost ^a	Cost-Converged ^a
Fibonacci & List, Performance Opt	2.12	2.05
Fibonacci & List, Cost Opt	2.81	1.86
Fibonacci & List, 50-50	2.25	2.25

^aMean cost per minute in dollars, based on the average execution time and number of requests in each cluster, for 512Mb function memory.

The results affirm that the adaptive system, particularly in the cost-optimized setup, achieves the most cost-effective operation, reducing the mean cost per minute substantially (up to 17%) post-convergence. This aspect accentuates the adaptive system's capacity to not only enhancing performance but also in ensuring a cost-efficient operational framework.

D. Concluding Remarks

Having scrutinized the performance across different configurations, a couple of key insights emerge. It is noticeable that the adaptive strategies, whether prioritizing performance or cost-efficiency, tend to offer advantages over a static approach, highlighting their flexibility.

Upon convergence, the adaptive strategies demonstrate notably reduced latencies and costs, albeit at the expense of higher initial latencies. However, starting from a 50-50 routing would allow the system to converge faster, eliminating the initial performance/cost variances. The expedited convergence seen with a 5-minute monitoring window comes as a testament to the system's responsiveness. Nevertheless, it also brings forth comparable latencies to the 10-minute window, showcasing a fine balance between convergence speed and performance outcomes.

Furthermore, the deviation in latencies, as analyzed, points to a greater consistency achieved post-convergence, especially in the performance-optimized setups. While the adaptive setups exhibit pronounced fluctuations initially, indicative of the system's efforts to find its optimal state, the post-convergence period witnesses a stabilization, thereby underscoring the adaptive system's efficacy in mitigating inconsistencies during runtime.

In light of the cost analysis, it is apparent that adaptive strategies not only steer towards optimal performance metrics

Fig. 10. Standard Deviation of Response Latency between different experiments.

but also drive down the costs significantly when compared to a rigid 50-50 strategy, thereby illustrating a dual advantage.

Conclusively, the results underscore the potential of adaptive strategies in orchestrating a system that is not only agile and responsive but also cost-efficient, paving the way for runtime adaptation in multi-cluster FaaS deployments that harmonizes performance optimization with economic viability.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A. Conclusion

In this work, we proposed and evaluated an adaptive routing service that integrates various functional components, including a Router, a Monitor, and a Forecaster, deployed over diverse infrastructural setups. The experimental results, analyzed over a series of comprehensive setups varying in routing strategies and monitoring intervals, underscore the system’s potential in optimizing performance and cost metrics.

Our system demonstrated a notable proficiency in reducing latency times, especially in the converged state, highlighting the benefit of adaptive routing strategies over static ones. While the initial stages of the adaptive system showed higher latencies owing to the 100-0 routing start point, the system converged to offer more efficient results compared to a static 50-50 baseline.

Moreover, the adaptive routing not only leveraged performance optimizations but also presented avenues for cost reductions, albeit with a slight increase in latency. The detailed cost analysis further bolstered the service’s proficiency in maintaining a favorable balance between cost and performance, outlining its potential in real-world applications.

B. Future Work

In our endeavor to further optimize the adaptive routing service, several promising avenues remain to be explored in future studies.

Firstly, incorporating more than two functions with diverse computational requirements into the experimental setup remains a vital frontier. Diving into this facet can facilitate a deeper understanding of how the adaptive system navigates varying computational demands.

Building on the findings from our initial experiments, there is a pertinent need to investigate the potential benefits of function-specific routing, which steers away from relying solely on the overall latency per cluster. By developing a routing strategy that considers each function’s individual characteristics and computational demands, we can potentially unlock a higher level of optimization, affording each function a computational environment that is more suitably tailored to its unique requirements.

Adding to this, we are keen to experiment with more advanced forecasting methods to enhance the service’s efficiency. Integrating exponential smoothing models that adapt more readily to the changes in data patterns stands as a plausible next step. Moreover, exploring alternative algorithms such as PID controllers could foster a more finely tuned adaptive routing system capable of predicting fluctuations with higher precision and adapting to changes more robustly [23].

In synthesizing these key aspects into our future experimental setups, we aim to foster a system that excels in efficiency, adaptability, and cost-effectiveness, crafting a pathway toward a more optimized runtime adaptation in serverless deployments.

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